

***Terminalia bellirica* mediated one-pot green synthesis of reduced graphene oxide-silver nanoparticle (RGO/AgNP) nanocomposite and its catalytic activity towards *p*-nitrophenol reduction in water**

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Abstract : We report a facile environmentally friendly one-pot synthetic route for the preparation of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite using *Terminalia bellirica* (*T. bellirica*) fruit extract as a reducing and stabilizing agent. The phenolic constituents of *T. bellirica* fruit extract played a key role in the reduction of both GO and Ag⁺ ions followed by uniform decoration of AgNPs onto the RGO surface. The obtained nanocomposite was characterized by UV-Visible, FTIR, XRD, SEM-EDS, TEM-SAED and Raman spectroscopy. The resultant nanocomposite exhibited excellent catalytic activity towards the reduction of 4-NP to 4-AP in the presence of NaBH₄ as reducing agent in water. The reduction reaction obeyed pseudo-first order kinetics and the rate constant was increased with increasing catalytic doses. Mechanisms for the synthesis of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite and catalytic reduction of 4-NP are discussed. This is a simple and low cost method for the fabrication of highly active catalyst material for the reduction of anthropogenic pollutant 4-NP in water.

Keywords : RGO/AgNP nanocomposite, *Terminalia bellirica*, green synthesis, 4-NP reduction.

Introduction

Graphene is a flat aromatic monolayer of sp²-bonded carbon atoms perfectly packed into a two-dimensional (2D) honeycomb lattice¹⁻³. It shows unique and extraordinary electronic, physical, mechanical, optical, thermal, and catalytic properties⁴ due to its large specific surface area (~2600 m² g⁻¹)⁵ and high electron mobility nature (~15000 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹)⁶. These properties highlight the importance of graphene based materials in different promising applications such as nanoelectronics⁷, fuel cells⁸, super capacitors⁵, sensors⁹ and catalysis¹⁰.

Several fabrication methods have been reported for the synthesis of graphene composites using different reducing agents such as sodium borohydride and hydrazine. However the graphene hybrids or reduced graphene oxide (RGO) has exhibited improved or modified surface properties due to chemical action between graphene surface and reducing agents^{11,12}. However, the utilization of stronger reducing agents such as hydrazine and sodium borohydride has made chemical strategies less suitable for the preparation of biologically important graphene hybrid

materials due to their high toxic, unstable and hazardous nature. On the other hand, the graphene hybrids prepared by green methods are prominent materials due to their biocompatibility and high aqueous dispensability as well as non-toxic nature. Subsequently, there is a rising demand for the alternative novel routes for the green, economical production of graphene composites in industrial scale for versatile applications.

Recently several research groups have focused on identifying a suitable eco-friendly, non-toxic and greener reducing materials for the synthesis of RGO in industrial scale due to their multifunctional ability in various applications¹³⁻¹⁵. During last few years green reducing agents like reducing sugar¹⁶, heparin¹⁷, protein bovine serum albumin¹⁸, dopamine¹⁹, poly(N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone) (PVP)²⁰ and L-ascorbic acid²¹ have been used for the reduction of graphene oxide (GO) to RGO. Recently our research group also has shown the ability of green reducing agents like casein²² and *Terminalia chebula* (*T. chebula*) seeds extract²³ for the deoxygenation of GO. A very few recent review articles have demonstrated the preparation

of RGO and RGO nanocomposites using green reducing sources²⁴⁻²⁷.

So far, different noble metal graphene composites such as RGO/Ag²⁸⁻³⁰, RGO/Au³¹, RGO/Pd³² and RGO/Pt³³ have been synthesized using RGO as substrate matrix for NPs anchoring. Among all these composites, RGO/Ag is recognised to be the most significant material due to its low cost with good conductivity, chemical stability, catalytic and antimicrobial activity.

In the present work we have used *T. bellirica* fruit pericarp extract as reducing and stabilizing agent for the synthesis of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. *T. bellirica* is a well-known deciduous tree, commonly habitats on the lower hills of Southeast Asia. It belongs to the family *Combretaceae*. Because of the presence of highly rich polyphenolic constituents, it has been widely used in ayurvedic medicines as a therapeutic agent. Natural polyphenols present in the fruit extract of *T. bellirica* can act as both reducing and stabilizing agent in the preparation of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. The resultant nanohybrids synthesized in this work was studied for its catalytic performance towards reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) in water.

Experimental

Materials :

Graphite flakes (100 mesh, 99.9995%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Bangalore. Sodium nitrate (NaNO₃), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%), potassium permanganate (KMnO₄), concentrated H₂SO₄ (98%), *p*-NP, NaBH₄ along with all other organic solvents were purchased from Sd fine Chemicals, Mumbai. AgNO₃ (Qualigens®, India) was used as received.

Preparation of plant extract :

T. bellirica fruits were collected from the local Vellore market, Tamilnadu, India. Fruit pericarp was separated, dried and finely grounded. Prior to extract preparation the dried powder was once again kept in an oven for about 20 min at 60 °C to ensure the complete removal of moisture. About 2.0 g of *T. bellirica* powder was taken into a beaker containing 100 mL of deionized water and heated in the temperature controlled water bath at 90 °C for about 1 h. The extract was filtered and used for the future experiments.

Preparation of GO :

A modified Hummer's method was followed for the chemical synthesis of graphene oxide (GO) using graphite flakes as an active precursor³⁴. Briefly, 0.5 g graphite flakes and 0.5 g sodium nitrate (NaNO₃) were dispersed with 23 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ (12.1 M) in a 250 mL round bottom flask. The reaction mixture was stirred for about 30 min in an ice bath maintained at 0 °C. To the above solution, potassium permanganate (4.0 g) was added gradually by maintaining the reaction temperature below 20 °C. Then the resultant mixture was allowed to stir for about 90 min at 40 °C, and the formed thick brown precipitate was mixed with 50 mL deionized water under vigorous stirring conditions. Finally, 6 mL H₂O₂ (30%) was added to the reaction mixture and the change in colour of the reaction mixture from dark brown to yellow indicated the formation of GO. The resulting GO suspension was washed several times with 5% HCl and deionized water in order to remove the excess of manganese salt until neutrality was attained. The purified GO was dried in an oven at 60 °C for about 1 h.

Preparation of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite :

GO dispersion was prepared by dispersing 50 mg of graphene oxide (GO) in 50 mL of double distilled water (1 mg/mL) under ultrasonic conditions for about 1 h. 10 mL of *T. bellirica* aqueous extract was added into the GO suspension under uniform stirring conditions. After 10 min, freshly prepared AgNO₃ (0.01 M) solution was added into the reaction vessel and change in colour of the solution was noticed from brown to yellowish brown. The resultant mixture was then refluxed on a water bath at 90 °C for a time period of 24 h for complete reduction of GO. The formed RGO/AgNP nanocomposite was settled down as black solid, which was then centrifuged and washed several times with double distilled water to remove the undesired residual components. The obtained RGO/AgNP powder was dried in an oven at 80 °C and stored for future experiments.

Characterization of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite :

Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Visible) spectroscopy :

UV-Visible spectral analysis data for the RGO/AgNP nanocomposites were generated by using a Jasco V-670 UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer. Measurements were carried out within the wavelength range from 200

nm to 800 nm against double distilled water as blank. Samples for UV-Vis analysis were prepared by dispersing the pure and dried form of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite in double distilled water under ultrasonic conditions.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) :

To know the functional groups that are present on the surface of GO and RGO/AgNP nanocomposite the dried samples were pelletized with KBr and then the spectra were recorded using JASCO FT-IR 4100 instrument over the wave number range of 4000–500 cm^{-1} in the diffuse reflectance mode at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) :

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis for the purified RGO/AgNP nanocomposite was performed at room temperature by using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) over the 2θ angle ranges from 3° – 80° at a scanning rate of $4^\circ/\text{min}$ with a step size of 0.02° . The instrument was calibrated against lanthanum hexaboride (LaB6) before the analysis.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) :

Carl Zeiss SEM instrument attached to EVO MA 15 was used for the SEM and EDX analysis. Images were taken at diverse magnification for the solid RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. Sample was spread over the surface of carbon tape attached to a metallic disk. Simultaneously the EDX spectrum measurements were carried out at particular areas on the solid surface of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite in order to acquire elemental distribution and morphology of the composite surface.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) :

To investigate the size and distribution pattern of AgNPs on RGO surface, the RGO/AgNP nanocomposite dispersion was observed under TEM (JEOL JEM 2100 HR-TEM) which was operated at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. TEM samples were prepared by dispersing dried RGO/AgNP nanocomposite in double distilled water (0.1 mg/mL) under ultrasonic conditions. A drop of well dispersed RGO/AgNP solution was placed on a lacey carbon coated copper grid and then evaporated under vacuum. The dried samples grids were then used for TEM analysis. A simultaneous measurement for the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern was also done.

Raman spectra :

Raman spectral analysis was carried out by using a Senterra R200-L (Bruker Optics) Raman spectrometer after passing the excitation line at 532 nm wavelength.

Catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) :

A standard catalytic test reaction was carried out in a quartz cuvette. For the catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol an appropriate amount of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite as a catalyst was added each time to the aqueous solution containing 1.9 mL 4-NP (0.3 mM) and 1 mL NaBH_4 (0.3 M) in a quartz cuvette and the disappearance of deep intense yellow colour indicated the completion of 4-NP reduction which was monitored with respect to time spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 400 nm. The initial concentration ratio of NaBH_4 to 4-NP was fixed to 100, because the concentration of NaBH_4 was treated as constant throughout the reaction conditions with respect to 4-NP.

Results and discussion

In this work an aqueous extract of *T. bellirica* fruits pericarp was used for the synthesis of RGO/Ag nanocomposite from GO and Ag^+ ions as illustrated in Fig. 1. The change of colour from yellowish brown to black indicated the formation of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. The formation of RGO/NP was prelimi-

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of *Terminalia bellirica* mediated reduction of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite.

narly monitored by using UV-Visible spectroscopy (Fig. 2). Fig. 2(a) denotes the absorption peaks of GO identified at 232 nm and 300 nm, which are assigned to the π - π^* and n - π^* transitions of the aromatic $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bonds respectively³⁵. On the other hand, Fig. 2(b) shows the UV-Visible absorption spectrum of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. Whenever *T. bellirica* fruit extract was added to the mixture of GO and Ag^+ ions, the simulta-

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectra of (a) GO (black) and (b) RGO/AgNP nanocomposite (red).

neous reduction reaction took place. The absorption peak of GO at 232 nm gradually red-shifted to 270 nm, and the absorption peak at 300 nm (shoulder peak) disappeared completely, indicating the restoration of electronic conjugation within the newly formed RGO due to more graphitic structure. Moreover, the doped metallic Ag^0 NPs on the surface of RGO are smaller in size and showed a new SPR absorbance peak at 423 nm.

Further, Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopic studies were performed for pure GO and RGO/AgNP nanocomposites (Fig. 3) in characterising the func-

tional groups that are present on the surfaces of both GO and RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. The band at 1043 cm^{-1} denotes the (C-O stretching), 1180 cm^{-1} corresponds to the (C-O-C stretching), 1724 cm^{-1} implies (C=O stretching) and the broad band at $3100\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ identified as -OH stretching band confirms the presence of various functional groups like carbonyl, carboxylic, epoxy and hydroxyl moieties on the surface of GO (Fig. 3a)³⁶. The removals of these oxygen-containing functional moieties of GO in RGO/AgNP nanocomposite are clearly reflected further by the disappearance of the prior mentioned bands. And therefore a relative decrease in the intensity of the broad band at $3100\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed as the -OH group attributed the successful reduction of GO (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 4 shows the XRD patterns of GO and synthesised RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. Pure graphite powder displays a sharp single diffraction peak from the plane (002) at 2θ (26.4°) with a typical inter-planar d-spacing value of 3.34 \AA (data not shown)³⁷. However for the prepared GO it exhibits a strong peak at 2θ of 10.49° corresponding to the plane (002) with inter-planar d-spacing value of 8.42 \AA (Fig. 4a) which indicates that the graphite had been oxidized successfully by intercalating the water and other oxygen containing moieties in between the graphite layer through modified Hummers method (Fig. 4b). GO is readily converted into its RGO in presence of *T. bellirica* aqueous extract, which is later confirmed by the disap-

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of (a) GO (black) and (b) RGO/AgNP nanocomposite (blue).

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of (a) GO (black) and (b) RGO/AgNP nanocomposite (red).

pearance of the peak at 2θ of 10.49° . On the other hand, the presence of four major peaks in the XRD pattern of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite appear at 2θ of 38.1° , 44.3° , 64.5° and 77.4° corresponding to the (111), (200), (220) and (311) planes of the cubic Ag crystal (JCPD : 96-110-0137) respectively indicating the decoration of metallic AgNPs onto the surface of RGO after reduction. The Bragg lattice parameter of the prepared face-centered cubic (fcc) structure of AgNPs is found to be 4.0855 \AA , indicating the presence of AgNPs loaded onto the surface of the RGO.

The surface morphology of GO and RGO/AgNP nanocomposite was investigated by SEM analysis (Figs. 5A and 5B) which clearly shows the existence of GO sheets as closely packed lamellar structures. Figs. 5C and 5D show the deposition of metallic Ag^0 crystallites onto the surface of RGO. The surface morphology of RGO sheets reveals the curled and corrugated nature. Additionally, the presence of Ag^0 crystallites may act as spacers to separate the neighbouring RGO sheets. Moreover, the EDS spectrum of the prepared RGO/AgNP nanocomposite shows the presence of elements such as C, O and Ag confirms the deposition of AgNPs onto the surface of RGO. However, the higher percentage of carbon content compared to that of oxygen indicates the reduction of GO to RGO.

The successful preparation of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite was further examined by TEM studies (Figs. 6A and 6B). It is seen that the formed AgNPs are hexago-

Fig. 5. SEM images of (A, B) GO and (C, D) RGO/AgNP nanocomposite, (E) EDS of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite.

Fig. 6. Typical TEM images of (A, B) RGO/AgNP nanocomposite and the SAED pattern of (C) RGO/AgNPs nanocomposite.

nal in shape and uniformly distributed onto the RGO substrate, confirming the formation of RGO/AgNP

nanocomposite. The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (Fig. 6C) reveals the presence of characteristic Debye rings for the fcc AgNPs with corresponding planes of (111), (200), (220) and (311), confirming the decoration of AgNPs onto the RGO surface.

Raman spectroscopy is an extensively used technique to sort out the structural disorders and defects in the carbon-based nanomaterials. The Raman spectra of GO and RGO/AgNP nanocomposite (Fig. 7) show the presence of two fundamental vibrational peaks at 1600 cm^{-1} and 1350 cm^{-1} respectively, which corresponds to G and D bands

Fig. 7. Raman spectra of (a) GO (red) and (b) RGO/AgNP nanocomposite (black).

of graphene. The G band signifies the first-order scattering of the E_{2g} phonon of sp^2 carbon atoms, while the D band illustrates the disorder-induced mode of local defects and structural imperfections originating from a breathing k-point phonon with A_{1g} symmetry^{38–40}. The intensity ratio of D band to G band (I_D/I_G) correlates to the average size of the sp^2 domains⁴¹. The I_D/I_G ratios for the prepared GO and RGO/AgNP nanocomposite are found to be 1.62 and 1.73, respectively. This increase in the I_D/I_G ratio may be due to the adsorption of polyphenols onto the graphene surface causing the increase in the D band of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. The deposited AgNPs onto the RGO surface may exhibit surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) effect^{42,43} due to increasing defect rate in the graphene structure which may be another possible reason for the higher I_D/I_G ratio of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite compared to GO.

The mechanism for the formation and stabilization of

RGO/AgNP nanocomposite by *T. bellirica* fruit extract is discussed elsewhere^{23,27}. *T. bellirica* extract contains polyphenols such as ascorbic acid, gallic acid, pyrogallol, methyl gallate and resorcinol. These polyphenols act as reducing and stabilizing agent for the formation of AgNPs which are later distributed onto the RGO surface. The presence of major content of gallic acid in the aqueous extract of *T. bellirica* fruit imparts dual activity i.e. reduces Ag^+ ions to metallic Ag^0 and GO to RGO successively, also stabilizes the formed AgNPs and RGO sheets from coalescing with each other by preventing nucleation, resulting the highly dispersible colloids.

The catalytic nature of the RGO/AgNP nanocomposite was manifested using the reduction of 4-NP to 4-aminophenol (4-AP) in the presence of $NaBH_4$ as an exemplified model reaction. A strong absorbance peak is noticed at 317 nm for 4-NP (data not shown). It was red shifted to 400 nm when $NaBH_4$ was added due to the deprotonation of 4-NP⁴⁴. The colour of 4-NP solution changed from light yellow to intense yellow colour which clearly indicated the formation of 4-nitrophenolate ion. However, the reduction reaction was not progressed even after 2 to 3 days in the presence of $NaBH_4$ alone. In order to accelerate the rate of reduction of 4-NP to 4-AP by $NaBH_4$, metal nanoparticles have been extensively used as catalyst. Noble metal nanoparticles such as AgNPs, AuNPs and PtNPs are well known to expedite electron transfer from donors (in this case BH_4^-) to acceptors (in this case 4-NP)⁴⁵. Thus, the colour intensity of 4-nitrophenolate ion solution decreases with respect to time after the addition of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite. Further, the reaction kinetics was studied by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer keeping the concentration of $NaBH_4$ constant. Fig. 8 shows the gradual decrease in the absorption of characteristic peak of 4-nitrophenolate ion at 400 nm, while the formation of a new peak appears at 297 nm assigned to 4-AP (Fig. 8, Fig. S1). This result shows that the reaction was completed within 280 s to 220 s at 25 °C which demonstrates the spontaneity and high speed catalytic nature of the synthesized RGO/AgNP nanocomposite towards the reduction of 4-NP.

The probable reaction steps that were involved in the catalytic decomposition of 4-NP to 4-AP in water are as follows. It is well known that $NaBH_4$ acts as a hydride generating source by undergoing hydrolysis at room tem-

Fig. 8. UV-Visible spectra of the reduction kinetics of 4-NP to 4-AP using RGO/AgNP nanocomposite (0.075 mg/mL) as catalyst.

perature and leads to liberation of hydrogen gas. This is catalytically favoured by metals and nanometals⁴⁶. It has been suggested that the catalytic decomposition of BH_4^- by AgNPs into two reactive intermediate species such as H-Ag and AgBH_3^- (eq. (1))⁴⁷, takes place as follows.

These species are the primarily responsible units for the reduction of 4-NP to 4-AP (eqs. (2) and (3)) stoichiometrically. A six electron generating reduction process are required for the conversion of 4-NP to 4-AP.

In order to evaluate the catalytic rate of 4-NP reduction, a very high concentration of NaBH_4 was taken and hence reaction follows a pseudo-first order kinetics^{48,49}. In this regard, the ratio of absorbance “ A_t ” of 4-NP at time “ t ” to that of “ A_0 ” measured at “ t_0 ” should be equal to the concentration ratio C_t/C_0 of 4-NP.

For the reduction reaction the kinetic equation can be written as follows :

$$\frac{dC_t}{dt} = -K_{\text{app}}C_t \text{ or } \ln\left(\frac{C_t}{C_0}\right) \text{ or } \ln\left(\frac{A_t}{A_0}\right) = -K_{\text{app}}t \quad (4)$$

where “ C_t ” denotes concentration of 4-NP at particular time period “ t ”, K_{app} is the apparent rate constant, which can be attained from the decrease in the intensity of the peak at 400 nm over time.

The catalytic reduction of 4-NP (0.3 mM) with NaBH_4

(0.3 M) at 25 °C is presented in Fig. 9a. It is observed that the reduction rates increased continuously with an increase in the catalytic amount of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite as a catalyst (0.025, 0.050, 0.075 mg/mL). The pseudo-first order rate constant (k) at 25 °C is calculated from the slope as 0.12 min^{-1} , 0.20 min^{-1} and 0.66 min^{-1} , respectively. The corresponding pseudo-first order rate constants (k) and R^2 values are reported in Table 1. We can further confirm that the RGO/AgNP nanocomposite could be acted as a suitable catalyst for the reduction of 4-NP with NaBH_4 as reducing agent.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants and R^2 values for the reduction of 4-NP using NaBH_4 as reducing agent and RGO/AgNP nanocomposites as catalyst

W_{cat} (mg/mL)	p -NP (mM)	Temp. (°C)	K (min^{-1})	R^2
0.025	0.3	25	0.122	0.9925
0.050	0.3	25	0.201	0.9985
0.075	0.3	25	0.660	0.9876
0.1	0.1	25	0.660	0.9900
0.1	0.2	25	0.661	0.9963
0.1	0.3	25	0.864	0.9957

Fig. 9b implies the effect of 4-NP concentration on the catalytic reduction time of 4-NP (0.1 to 0.3 mM) in the presence of constant amount of NaBH_4 (0.3 M) as reducing agent and RGO/AgNPs nanocomposite as catalyst (0.1 mg/mL) at 25 °C. The respective pseudo-first order rate constants (k) at 25 °C are calculated from the slope as 0.660 min^{-1} , 0.661 min^{-1} and 0.864 min^{-1} . The corresponding pseudo-first order rate constants (k), R^2 values are reported in Table 1. It also indicates that the reaction rate was increased with increase in the initial concentration of 4-NP. This concept of phenomenon is somewhat different from the earlier studies and the present study results suggest that the RGO surface acts as a solid support and increase catalytic activity synergistically (Fig. S2). The synergistically enhanced catalytic activity can be better explained as follows : the 4-NP is π -rich in nature and hence can be adsorbed easily onto the surface of RGO substrate via π - π stacking interactions⁵⁰. When the concentration of 4-NP is higher nearer to the AgNPs onto RGO surface, leads to more efficient contact between 4-NP and AgNPs. On the other hand, in the absence of RGO support, 4-NP may collide with Ag nanocolloids by chance and remains intact with the catalyst during reduc-

Fig. 9. Plots of $\ln(C_t/C_0)$ versus time for the catalytic reduction of 4-NP with NaBH_4 ; (a) by different amounts of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite; (b) by RGO/AgNP nanocomposite at different 4-NP concentrations, C_0 and C_t denote the concentrations of 4-NP at $t = 0$ and $t = t$, respectively with $[\text{NaBH}_4]/[\text{p-NP}] = 100$.

tion. When this process is not attained, 4-NP easily comes back into solution phase and reduction process will not proceed.

Conclusions

In summary, we have demonstrated a green, low-cost effective method for the synthesis of RGO/AgNP nanocomposite by using *T. bellirica* fruit pericarp aqueous extract. The polyphenols of the extract have acted both as reducing and stabilizing agents for GO and Ag^+ ions. The formed AgNPs have distributed uniformly onto the surface of the RGO substrate. The RGO/AgNP nanocomposite has exhibited excellent catalytic activity towards the reduction of 4-NP to 4-AP with NaBH_4 in water. The plausible mechanism for the catalytic reduction of 4-NP in the presence of NaBH_4 with RGO/AgNP

nanocomposite has suggested synergistic effect of RGO substrate. Such a product with more potential properties could be utilized in the treatment of industrial waste water containing 4-NP under mild conditions. This paper further will open up an environmentally friendly method to synthesize biocompatible RGO/AgNP nanocomposites in large scale by using naturally occurring polyphenols rich plant extracts. This in turn will decrease or replace the utility of existing hazardous or toxic reducing and stabilizing agents for the synthesis of RGO based nanocomposites.

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